

PERFORMANCE PROPERTIES OF THE SURFACE OF PARTS

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Annotation. The article presents one of the ways to achieve increased performance properties of the part, due to the hardening of the surface layer, the formation of a favorable stress-strain state in the layer.

Keywords: diamond burnishing, diamond, roughness, contact pressure, plastic deformation, hardening of the surface layer, material hardness.

The achievement of increased performance properties occurs mainly due to: strengthening the surface layer of the part, the formation of a favorable stress-strain state in the layer, and due to a high degree of surface finishing [1].

Diamond burnishing has advantages associated with the physical and mechanical properties of diamond. Due to its high hardness and thermal conductivity, diamond has a low coefficient of friction against metal. To achieve low roughness of the smoothed surface, the working surface of the diamond can be polished to $Rz = 0.025\text{--}0.063\ \mu\text{m}$. The main distinguishing feature of diamond burnishing, as opposed to rolling, is the ability to process parts with very high hardness. Diamond has a low coefficient of friction on metal and a small contact area. The smoothing force is in the range of 50–300 N, which makes it possible to process non-rigid parts (thin-walled bushings and shafts) [1].

For ironing, simple devices are used that are installed on universal machines, which makes this process attractive. Contact pressure when using diamond burnishing is generated by the radial force that acts between the surface of the diamond and the part. If the contact pressure is higher than the yield strength, then plastic deformation occurs in the thin surface layer, which acquires a specific fibrous structure, while the original crystal lattice is distorted. When the metal is strengthened during diamond burnishing, dislocations are concentrated near the shear line. Since dislocations are surrounded by elastic stress fields, subsequent plastic deformations (dislocation movements) require greater stress than in unstrengthened metal. Plastic deformation is accompanied by hardening of the surface layer, as a result of which the plasticity decreases and the hardness of the material increases. At a certain depth, plastic deformations turn into elastic ones and become equal to zero at a sufficient distance from the surface. Due to the uneven deformation along the depth of the elastic-plastically deformed layer during diamond burnishing, residual stresses

are formed, the magnitude and nature of which depend on the modes and conditions of burnishing. During diamond burnishing, the role of technological heredity in the physical and mechanical characteristics of the surface layer increases. During diamond burnishing, the layer is not removed, but undergoes additional elastoplastic deformation. The magnitude and depth of penetration of this additional deformation depends on the sign, magnitude and nature of the occurrence of previously induced residual stresses. There are two ways you.

Burnishing with rigid fastening of the tool, there is a rigid kinematic connection between the tool and the part. The smoother is mounted on the machine like a cutter, and its position relative to the workpiece is determined only by the kinematics of the machine and the elasticity of the AIDS system. During processing, the smoother is embedded into the surface being processed by a certain amount, which depends on the plasticity of the material being processed, the surface roughness and the radius of the smoother and ranges from several microns to several hundredths of a millimeter. The ability to increase the accuracy of the dimensions and shape of the workpiece by redistributing the volume of plastically deformable metal and the ability to process discontinuous surfaces is an advantage of this method. However, when the smoother is rigidly fixed, due to the runout of the workpiece, the amount of penetration of the smoother and, consequently, the smoothing force can fluctuate within significant limits. As a result of uneven pressure on the treated surface, the latter has unequal roughness and is heterogeneous in physical and mechanical properties. Therefore, during hard burnishing, high demands are placed on the rigidity and accuracy of the installation of parts and tools.

Ironing with elastic fastening of the tool is a simpler and more convenient method. With this method of smoothing, the tool is elastically pressed against the workpiece using a spring or other means. The force of pressing the smoother against the part, depending on the plasticity of the material being processed, the surface roughness and the radius of the smoother, is easily controlled and maintained constant during processing. In this case, there is no rigid kinematic connection between the part and the smoother, and the position of the latter relative to the part is determined by itself; treated surface. When the smoother is elastically fastened, the shape errors of the parts are copied and are not corrected. Only the surface roughness is smoothed and hardened.

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